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Requirement Consolidation (PerReC)
Activity

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**M. Höpfner³, Q. Errera², B. Funke⁴, B. Monge-Sanz⁵, P.
Preusse¹, B.-M. Sinnhuber³, J. Ungermann¹**

¹**Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ)**, *Wilhelm-Johnen-Straße, 52428 Jülich, Germany*

²**Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB)**, *Ringlaan 3 Avenue Circulaire, 1180 Brussels, Belgium*

³**Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)**, *Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany*

⁴**Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (CSIC)**, *Gta. de la Astronomía, s/n, 18008 Granada, Spain*

⁵**University of Oxford (Oxford)**, *Wellington Square, Oxford, OX1 2JD, United Kingdom*

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Reference list extracted from Zotero library differentiating by CAIRT reports, peer-reviewed publication and other key publications, documents.		
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<i>Names of authors</i> M. Höpfner, Q. Errera, B. Funke, B. Monge-Sanz, P. Preusse, B.-M. Sinnhuber, J. Ungermann		
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1 References: CAIRT mission science study documents and reports

Ref	Deliverable ID (Study)	Ref number	Title	Current version	Version date	Public (*) Y/N
[1]	DEL-02-(SciReC)	DEL-02-TN-1-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Consolidated Inputs and Recommendations to MATER	1.0	17.06.2022	
[2]	DEL-03 (SciReC)	DEL-03-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1	Science Traceability Matrix	1.1	17.11.2023	Y
[3]	DEL-04 (SciReC)	DEL-04-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	High-level data processing and calibration steps flow-chart	1.0	15.09.2022	Y
[4]	DEL-05 (SciReC)	DEL-05-TN2-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.2	CAIRT Phase 0 plan for performance assessment and tracing to scientific goals	1.2	30.10.2023	Y
[5]	DEL-07 (SciReC)	DEL-07-TN3-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1	Verification of mission performance simulation tools	1.1	26.01.2023	Y
[6]	DEL-08 (SciReC)	DEL-08-02-TN4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC_1.3	Anticipated Mission performance at Phase-0	1.3	25.10.2023	Y
[7]	DEL-09 (SciReC)	DEL-09-TN5-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1	Level-2 ATBDs	1.1	19.10.2023	Y
[8]	DEL-10 (SciReC)	DEL-10-TN6-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.2	Tracing mission requirements to mission objectives and scientific goals	1.2	27.10.2023	Y
[9]	DEL-11 (SciReC)	DEL-11-TN7-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1	Consolidated Inputs to MRD	1.1	12.01.2024	
[10]	DEL-12.1 (SciReC)	DEL-12-TN-8.1-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Effect of calibration gaps on temperature resolution	1.0	16.11.2022	Y
[11]	DEL-12.2 (SciReC)	DEL-12-TN-8.2-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Effect of PSF on temperature resolution	1.0	22.12.2022	Y
[12]	DEL-12.3 (SciReC)	DEL-12-TN-8.3-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Quality of the SF6 volume mixing ratio retrieval depending on different spectral resolutions	1.0	01.01.2023	Y
[13]	DEL-12.4 (SciReC)	DEL-12-TN-8.4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Technical note on pointing jitter	1.2	16.02.2023	Y
[14]	DEL-12.5 (SciReC)	DEL-12-TN-8.5-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Impact of clouds on CAIRT L2 performances	1.0	05.04.2023	Y

[15]	DEL-12.6 (SciReC)	DEL-12-TN-8.6-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Minimum Altitude of Deep Space Calibration	1.0	18.10.2023	Y
[16]	DEL-12.7 (SciReC)	DEL-12-TN-8.7-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Study of the synergy between CAIRT and IASI-NG/Sentinel 5	1.0	27.11.2023	Y
[17]	DEL-15 (SciReC)	DEL-15-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.2	SRA-2: "Scientific Readiness self-Assessment"	1.2	24.11.2023	Y
[18]	DEL-16 (SciReC)	DEL-16-TN10-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1	Phase A scientific roadmap	1.1	28.11.2023	Y
[19]	DEL-17 (SciReC)	DEL-17-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Executive Summary Report	1.0	24.01.2024	Y
[20]	DEL-19 (SciReC)	DEL-19-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0	Contract Closure Documentation	1.0	24.01.2024	N
[21]	DEL-SW-DATA-GA (SciReC)	DEL-SW-DATA-GA-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC.1.0	SW-1, SW-2, DATA-1, DATA-2, GA-1	1.0	24.11.2023	Y
[22]	DEL-01 (PerReC)	DEL-01-SRA-1-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-0.1	CAIRT Scientific Readiness Assessment 1	0.1	16.04.2024	N
[23]	DEL-03 (PerReC)	DEL-03-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.3	Scientific applications, end-user, and observation requirements for the CAIRT mission	1.4	23.01.2026	Y
[24]	DEL-04-01a (PerReC)	DEL-04-01a-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.1	CAIRT linear SWB ATBD	2.1	20.11.2025	Y
[25]	DEL-04-01b (PerReC)	DEL-04-01b-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1	CAIRT JURASSIC2 ATBD	1.1	26.09.2025	Y
[26]	DEL-04-01c (PerReC)	DEL-04-01c-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.2	CAIRT Level 2 ATBD	1.2	01.10.2025	Y
[27]	DEL-04-01d (PerReC)	DEL-04-01d-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0	ATBD-KOPRA	1.0	14.10.2024	Y
[28]	DEL-04-02 (PerReC)	DEL-04-02-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for CAIRT product L2b overview	1.1	16.09.2025	Y
[29]	DEL-04-03a (PerReC)	DEL-04-03a-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.1	Core of technical paper on GWBG removal	2.1	06.11.2025	Y
[30]	DEL-04-03b (PerReC)	DEL-04-03b-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0	GWBG Core of technical paper on GW	2.0	19.01.2026	Y

[31]	DEL-04-03c (PerReC)	DEL-04-03c-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-2.0	Core of technical paper on AoA - On the estimation of stratospheric age of air from correlations of multiple trace gases	2.0	02.07.2025	Y
[32]	DEL-05 (PerReC)	DEL-05-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v3.1	PSD: "CAIRT L2(+) Product Specification Document"	3.1	01.12.2025	Y
[33]	DEL-06 (PerReC)	DEL-06-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.1	Product Validation Plan	1.1	23.10.2025	Y
[34]	DEL-07 (PerReC)	DEL-07-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-2.0	CAIRT Mission Performance Evaluation Plan (MPEP)	2.0	08.09.2025	N
[35]	DEL-08 (PerReC)	DEL-08-TN2-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v1.3	CAIRT Test Data Sets for Mission Performance Evaluation - Technical Note TN-2	1.3	19.11.2025	N
[36]	DEL-09 (PerReC)	DEL-09-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v3.1	CAIRT measurement requirements assessment - Technical Note TN-3	3.1	19.11.2025	Partly
[37]	DEL-09.1 (PerReC)	DEL-09.1-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v6.0	Technical note on Yaw-steering for CAIRT	6.0	10.10.2025	Y
[38]	DEL-09.2 (PerReC)	DEL-09.2-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v5.0	Technical note on pointing jitter	5.0	04.03.2024	Y
[39]	DEL-09.3 (PerReC)	DEL-09.3-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v3.0	Technical note on spectral calibration	3.0	21.10.2024	Y
[40]	DEL-09.4 (PerReC)	DEL-09.4-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v5.0	Technical note on diffraction/far field SEDF	5.0	10.10.2025	Y
[41]	DEL-09.5 (PerReC)	DEL-09.5-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.0	Technical note on L2 performance for FOV widths 1.4 km vs 1.5 km	1.0	11.10.2024	Y
[42]	DEL-09.6 (PerReC)	DEL-09.6-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-6.0	Technical note on SEDF requirement	6.0	09.10.2025	Y
[43]	DEL-09.7 (PerReC)	DEL-09.7-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.0	Technical note on horizontal vs. vertical atmospheric variability	1.0	16.08.2024	Y
[44]	DEL-09.8 (PerReC)	DEL-09.8-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-2.0	Technical note analog-digital discretization error	2.0	10.10.2025	Y
[45]	DEL-09.9 (PerReC)	DEL-09.9-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.1	Technical Note: Influence of calibration gaps and dead subsamples	1.1	08.10.2025	Y
[46]	DEL-09-10	DEL-09.10-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.0	Technical note on cloud influence	1.0	22.09.2025	Y
[47]	DEL-10 (PerReC)	DEL-10-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-v2.1	Evaluation of CAIRT scientific performance in Phase A through	2.1	19.11.2025	Partly

			analysis and demonstration - Technical Report TR-1			
[48]	DEL-10-2 (PerReC)	DEL-10.2-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.1	Uncertainty estimation of gravity wave parameters by Monte Carlo Simulation	1.1	14.01.2026	Y
[49]	DEL-12 (PerReC)	DEL-12-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-2.0	Scientific and societal relevance and impact studies for the CAIRT mission	2.0	02.10.2025	Y
[50]	DEL-13 (PerReC)	DEL-13-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.0	CAIRT Mission Impact Assessment Plan - MIAP	1.0	17.10.2024	N
[51]	DEL-14-1(PerReC)	DEL-14-1-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.0	Readme-1: CAIRT mission test data set product descriptions for impact study on Age of Air	1.0	19.09.2025	Y
[52]	DEL-14-2 (PerReC)	DEL-14-2-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-3.0	Readme-2: CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for case/impact studies for Consistent simulation of GW and MLT	3.0	16.01.2026	Y
[53]	DEL-14-3 (PerReC)	DEL-14-3-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-2.0	Readme-3: CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for case/impact studies for geoengineering	2.0	18.11.2025	Y
[54]	DEL-14-4 (PerReC)	DEL-14-4-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-2.0	Readme-4: CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for case/impact studies UTLS O3 OSSE	2.0	19.09.2025	Y
[55]	DEL-14-5 (PerReC)	DEL-14-5-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.1	Readme-5: CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for impact study Stratosphere/UTLS and weather and climate predictability	1.1	23.01.2026	Y
[56]	DEL-14-6 (PerReC)	DEL-14-6-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-2.0	Readme-6: CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for case/impact studies for volcanic ash detection	2.0	26.09.2025	Y
[57]	DEL-15-1 (PerReC)	DEL-15-1-TR2.1- CAIRT-PhAPerReC- 1.0	CAIRT Case / Impact Study 1 for AoA	1.0	17.10.2025	Y
[58]	DEL-15-2 (PerReC)	DEL-15-2-TR2.2- CAIRT-PhAPerReC- 1.1	CAIRT Case / Impact Study 2 for consistent simulation of GW and MLT	1.1	29.09.2025	Y
[59]	DEL-15-3 (PerReC)	DEL-15-3-TR2.3- CAIRT-PhAPerReC- 3.0	CAIRT Case / Impact Study 3 Geoengineering via Stratospheric Sulfur Injection	3.0	30.09.2025	Y

[60]	DEL-15-4 (PerReC)	DEL-15-TR2.4-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1	CAIRT Case / Impact Study 4 for UTLS O3 OSSE	1.1	14.01.2026	Y
[61]	DEL-15-5 (PerReC)	DEL-15-TR2.5-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0	CAIRT Case / Impact Study 5 for Stratosphere/UTLS and weather and climate prediction	1.0	23.01.2026	Y
[62]	DEL-15-6 (PerReC)	DEL-15-TR2.6-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0	CAIRT Case / Impact Study 6 for volcanic ash	2.0	03.07.2025	Y
[63]	DEL-16 (PerReC)	DEL-16-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.3	CAIRT bibliographic reference list	2.3	22.01.2026	Y
[64]	DEL-18 (PerReC)	DEL-18-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0	SRM: “Scientific roadmap for CAIRT beyond Phase A/B1”	1.0	15.10.2025	N
	DEL-19 (PerReC)	D-19-TR3/FR:	Consolidated inputs for the CAIRT Report for Mission Selection	1.0	20.01.2026	N RfMS->Y
[65]	DEL-21 (PerReC)	DEL-21-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1	Peer-reviewed publications (or manuscripts in review) based on CAIRT scientific work	1.1	20.01.2026	N
[66]	DEL-22 (PerReC)	DEL-22-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.2	Record of dissemination and outreach activities	1.2	20.01.2026	N
[67]	DEL-24 (PerReC)	DEL-24-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.2	Executive Summary Report	1.2	22.01.2026	Y
[68]	DEL-25 (PerReC)	DEL-25-CAIRT-PhAPerReC	Contract Closure Documentation	1.0	23.01.2026	N
[69]	DEL- DATA-SW-LIB-WEB (PerReC)	DEL- DATA-SW-LIB- WEB-CAIRT- PhAPerReC-1.4	DATA-01, DATA-02, DATA-03, LIB-01, LIB-02, LIB-03, SW-01, WEB-01	1.4	11.12.2025	Y

(*) CAIRT study documents marked “Y” will not contain confidential or proprietary information, are intended for public dissemination once accepted and finalised, will be accessible via Zenodo public repository, and will be findable via <https://zenodo.org/communities/cairt-scirec/records> site.

2 References: CAIRT mission science study publications

Ref	Lead author(s)	Title
[70]	Rhode et al.	Global-scale gravity wave analysis methodology for the ESA Earth Explorer 11 candidate CAIRT
[71]	Voet et al.	On the estimation of stratospheric age of air from correlations of multiple trace gases
[72]	Tirelli et al.	Extension of the Complete Data Fusion algorithm to tomographic retrieval products
[73]	Johansson et al.	Ammonia in the upper troposphere–lower stratosphere (UTLS): GLORIA airborne measurements for CAMS model evaluation in the Asian monsoon and in biomass burning plumes above the South Atlantic

[74]	Wetzel et al.	Stratospheric and upper tropospheric measurements of long-lived tracers and photochemically active species with GLORIA-B'. Gases/Remote Sensing/Validation and Intercomparisons
[75]	Mathew et al.	GLOFI – A methodology and toolbox for scale-separation of satellite observations for analysis of gravity waves
[76]	Rhode	Identifying Orographic Gravity Waves in 3D Observations via Backward Ray Tracing
[77]	Errera et al.	On the capability of the Changing Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography explorer (CAIRT) candidate mission to constrain O3 and H2O in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere

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[79]	Griessbach et al.	Characterisation of particulates in the upper troposphere / lower stratosphere: Final Report: ESA Contract 400011677/16/NL/LvH
[80]	Kerridge et al.	PREMIER - Consolidation of Requirements and Synergistic Retrieval Algorithms: Final Report: ESA contract 4200022848/09/NL/CT
[81]	Riese et al.	PREMIER - Quantification of Atmospheric Pollution and Climate Aspects: Final Report: ESA contract AO/1-6340/09/NL/CBI
[82]	Spang et al.	PremierEX: Final Report: ESA contract 22670/09/NL/CT
[83]	Preusse et al.	Observation of gravity waves from space: Final Report: ESA Contract CN/22561/09/NL/AF
[84]	Salawitch et al.	The Imminent Data Desert: The Future of Stratospheric Monitoring in a Rapidly Changing World
[85]	Ungermann et al.	Technical Assistance for the CAIRT Experiment (CAIRTEX) by means of a Balloon-borne Limb sounding Campaign in Canada (Final Report)

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Already in Ph0 a Zotero Library was established that continuously grew during PhA.

<https://www.zotero.org/groups/4393603/cairt?token=urbp86al4ixjzcsdhfztfpaz9ty1627efqlvjw50>

The Library is maintained by KIT (Michael Höpfner) and access can be applied for there.

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- [2] M. Höpfner, B.-M. Sinnhuber, Q. Errera, B. Funke, P. Preusse, and P. Raspollini, 'Science Traceability Matrix', DEL-03-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1, Nov. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://bwsyncandshare.kit.edu/s/97pPqFC5s28E2An>
- [3] J. Ungermann, 'High-level data processing and calibration steps flow-chart', DEL-04-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0, Sep. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://bwsyncandshare.kit.edu/s/cz3L2qj4yidNBbS>

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